

ASYMPTOTIC PERFORMANCE MEASURES FOR SEQUENTIAL PARTITION DETECTORS

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ABSTRACT

It is known that the sequential probability ratio test (SPRT) minimizes the average detection time among all tests for fixed type I and type II errors under the hypothesis and alternative. Often, in practical detection problems, the signal level is unknown during the decision interval. In this paper, the relative efficiency of a sequential detector is compared with its fixed sample size detector counterpart for signal levels which may be inconsistent with the assumed alternative. The results are applicable to detectors called partition detectors which are designed based on knowledge of a set of quantiles and related functions from the unknown noise field, and guarantee distribution-free performance under the hypothesis. For the class of sequential detectors that have boundaries which are linear functions of the sample size, the operating characteristic function and average sample number ASN are derived.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sequential tests based on the likelihood ratio (SPRT) are applied in cases where it is desired to reduce the average time to a decision. Wald (1) has shown that the SPRT is optimum in the sense that the average number of samples are minimum under a set of conditions. In these cases, the number of observations of the data is not fixed in advance, but is determined from a stopping rule associated with a receiver. However, the overall test length usually must be considered large enough, as will be the case herein, to justify the asymptotic performance results characterizing sequential detectors.

In many important applications in sonar and radar, the noise distribution cannot be assumed known. These problems are known as nonparametric because the distribution of the observables cannot be completely specified by a finite set of parameters. The approach we take in this case is to first reduce the observation space by partitioning it on the basis of knowledge of quantiles and related func-

tions.

This paper generalizes some of the results developed for sequentially detecting stochastic signals (2). Specifically, we are interested in detecting signals which are imbedded in additive noise. The noise distribution is not known and may be non-Gaussian or impulsive. The receiver is an array of sensors in which each sensor is partitioned into m -intervals. Details of this problem can be found in reference (2). Throughout this paper, we concentrate on the general form of the sequential detector for a class of stopping rules and compare its performance to a comparable fixed sample detector (FSD) based on the relative efficiency.

II. FIXED SAMPLE DETECTION

For a sequence of independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) random variables $\{T_i'\}$ $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, $T_i' = T(\bar{x}_i)$, as defined in reference (2), let

$$(1) \quad T_N = \sum_{i=1}^N T_i' ,$$

where N is a known fixed integer. The vector \bar{x}_i represents spatial dependence which need not be considered further in this analysis. From the central limit theorem (3) it can be shown that under mild regularity conditions on T_N ,

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} P_q \left\{ (T_N - E_q(T_N)) / (\text{VAR}_q(T_N))^{1/2} \right\} \rightarrow N(0, 1)$$

under the hypothesis $H_q(q=0)$ and alternative $H_q(q=1)$, where $N(0, 1)$ represents a normal distribution with zero mean and unit variance. The hypothesis, H_0 , and alternative, H_1 , correspond to the noise or signal and noise conditions respectively.

With these assumptions, the FSD statistic obeys the following error probabilities,

$$(2) \quad \begin{aligned} P(T_N > T_{I/H_0}) &= \alpha = 1 - \Phi(y_q), \\ P(T_N < T_{I/H_1}) &= \beta = \Phi(y_q), \end{aligned}$$

where T_L is a fixed threshold, $y_q = (T_L - E(T_N/H_q)) / (\text{VAR}(T_N/H_q))^{1/2}$, $q = 0, 1$,

and
$$\Phi(y_q) = (1/\sqrt{2\pi}) \int_{-\infty}^{y_q} \exp(-\frac{1}{2}z^2) dz.$$

The symbol $\Phi(y_q)$ represents the standard normal distribution. Solving for the threshold T_L in equation (2), we find the following expression,

$$(3) \quad E(T_N/H_1) - E(T_N/H_0) = \{\Phi^{-1}(1-\alpha) * (\text{VAR}(T_N/H_0))^{1/2} - \Phi^{-1}(\beta) (\text{VAR}(T_N/H_0))^{1/2}\}.$$

Substituting the mean and variance from equation (1) into equation (3), we obtain the following result,

$$(4) \quad N = \left\{ \Phi^{-1}(1-\alpha) (\text{VAR}(T_i^*/H_0))^{1/2} - \Phi^{-1}(\beta) (\text{VAR}(T_i^*/H_1))^{1/2} \right\}^2 / (E(T_i^*/H_1) - E(T_i^*/H_0))^2.$$

In reference (2) the following assumption was justified, $\text{VAR}(T_i^*/H_1) \sim \text{VAR}(T_i^*/H_0)$,

for a class of functions of interest, when $\theta_0 \leq \theta \leq \theta_1$, θ_1 sufficiently small and θ is a parameter of the detection statistic. The set (θ_0, θ_1) corresponds to (H_0, H_1) respectively.

Using this assumption, we can rewrite equation (4) as follows,

$$(5) \quad N = \left\{ \Phi^{-1}(1-\alpha) - \Phi^{-1}(\beta) \right\}^2 / d,$$

$$\text{where } d = (E(T_i^*/H_1) - E(T_i^*/H_0))^2 / \text{VAR}(T_i^*/H_0).$$

In equation (5), N depends upon α, β , and the parameter set (θ_0, θ_1) under H_0 and H_1 respectively. Given (θ_0, θ_1) , equation (5) represents the required N needed to guarantee the desired (α, β) . The power of the test (probability of detection) is defined as

$$P_d = 1 - \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(1-\alpha) - (Nd)^{1/2}).$$

III. SEQUENTIAL DETECTION

For the sequence of i.i.d. random variables given in equation (1), let $N=n$ be random in the sense that the sample size of the test is not fixed in advance, but is determined by the stopping time, $N = \inf\{n: T_n \notin (b, a)\}$, where $b < 0 < a$ are the Wald (3) thresholds. If $T_n \geq a$ or $T_n \leq b$ then H_1 or H_0 is accepted respectively.

The sequential detector SD statistic

follows as

$$(6) \quad T_n = K \sum_{i=1}^n (L_i - B),$$

where K and B are real constants. We require that T_n converge to $N(0, 1)$, as defined in Section II, with corresponding error probabilities as given in equation (2).

The fundamental identity (F.I.) of sequential analysis (1) is defined as follows,

$$(7) \quad E(\exp(T_n h) (\phi(h))^{-n}) = 1,$$

where H is real and $\phi(h)$ is the moment generating function of the common distribution of T_i^* which is assumed to exist.

From equation (7) the operating characteristic (OC) function can be shown to have the following form,

$$(8) \quad L(\delta) = \{ \exp(ah(\delta)) - 1 \} / \{ \exp(ah(\delta)) - \exp(bh(\delta)) \},$$

where δ is a parameter of the sequential test and $h(\delta)$ is defined as $H_0: h(\delta = \delta_0) = 1$ and $H_1: h(\delta = \delta_1) = -1$. We also define a critical point in which $h(\delta = \delta_c) = 0$. The corresponding power function of the SD is defined as $P(\delta) = 1 - L(\delta)$.

It was shown in reference (2) that a solution for h can be given by the following expression,

$$(9) \quad h = -2 E(T_i^*) / \text{VAR}(T_i^*) = -2(E(L_i) - B) / K \text{VAR}(L_i).$$

From the constraints $H_0: h=1$ and $H_1: h=-1$ the constants K and B of equation (9) can be found to be given by the following expressions (2),

$$(10) \quad K = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) (E(L_i/H_1) + E(L_i/H_0)),$$

$$B = (E(L_i/H_1) - E(L_i/H_0)) / \text{VAR}(L_i/H_0),$$

where we have assumed that the signal θ_1 was sufficiently small so that the approximation $\text{VAR}(L_i/H_1) \sim \text{VAR}(L_i/H_0)$ is justified.

Substituting equation (10) into equation (9) there follows the result, $h(\delta) = 1 - 2\delta/\delta_1$, where $\delta = (E_\theta(L_i) - E(L_i/H_0)) / \text{VAR}(L_i/H_0)^{1/2}$; $\delta_1 = (E(L_i/H_1) - E(L_i/H_0)) / \text{VAR}(L_i/H_0)^{1/2}$.

The symbol $E_\theta(L_i)$ represents the average value of L_i for $H_0: \theta=0$, $H_1: \theta=\theta_1$ and $0 \leq \theta \leq \theta_1$.

With the results of equations (8), (9), and (10), we can express the ASN for equation (6) as follows,

$$E(n) = (-2/hd) (aL(\delta) + b(1-L(\delta))), h \neq 0$$

$$(11) \quad E(n) = -ad/d, \quad h = 0.$$

At $h=1$, $h=-1$, or $h=0$, the minimum ASN is obtained in equation (11) by maximizing d . It should be clear from equation (11), that for other values of h given (θ_0, θ_1) the SD need not be optimum based solely on d .

IV. RELATIVE EFFICIENCY

The efficiency of the SD relative to the best competing FSD is developed in this section. The performance is measured in terms of the ratio of the fixed sample size to ASN. The ratio, called the relative efficiency RE, is expressed as follows,

$$RE = N/E(n) = -(\frac{1}{2}) h(\delta) (\Phi^{-1}(1-\alpha) - \Phi^{-1}(\beta))^2$$

$$(12) \quad \quad \quad * (aL(\delta) + b(1-L(\delta))),$$

$$\quad \quad \quad h(\delta) \neq 0$$

$$RE = (\Phi^{-1}(1-\alpha) - \Phi^{-1}(\beta))^2 / (-ab), \quad h(\delta) = 0$$

In applying equation (12), it should be recognized that the power curves of SD and FSD at $h = \pm 1$ are identical, however, at other values of δ or θ they may not be.

Recall that the boundaries a, b are functions of (α, β) (1). Assuming that α, β are small, we obtain the following approximations, $\alpha \sim \exp(-a)$ and $\beta \sim \exp(b)$. If we let $a, |b|$ become large, then equation (12) reduces to (4),

$$RE = -(\frac{1}{2}) h(\delta) ((2a)^{\frac{1}{2}} + (-2b)^{\frac{1}{2}})^2 (aL(\delta) + b(1-L(\delta))), \quad h \neq 0$$

$$(13)$$

$$RE = ((2a)^{\frac{1}{2}} + (-2b)^{\frac{1}{2}})^2 / (-ab), \quad h = 0.$$

For simplicity, let $a = |b|$, then as $a \rightarrow \infty$ we obtain, asymptotically, from equation (13), the result,

$$\lim_{a \rightarrow \infty} RE = \begin{cases} 4, & h = 1 \\ 4, & h = -1 \\ 0, & h = 0 \\ \infty, & \text{if } h \rightarrow \infty. \end{cases}$$

At $h = \pm 1$ the SD is 4 times more efficient, asymptotically, than its FSD counterpart. However, at the critical point, $h = 0$, the SD efficiency approaches zero, asymptotically, in terms of the RE. Similar results were obtained in references (5), (6), and (7).

It is of interest to determine if there are any finite values of a, b for which the $RE \geq 1$ at $h=0$.

Let $\alpha = \beta$ and set $RE=1$, in equation (12) at $h=0$. Then we obtain the result, $\alpha = \beta \geq .008$ for $RE \geq 1$ at $h=0$. This result, which was also obtained in reference (6), represents an obvious limitation on the desired performance characteristics of a

practical system employing sequential detectors designed with fixed thresholds. If $\alpha = \beta = 10^{-4}$ then $RE \geq .618$. However, if $\alpha = 10^{-4}, \beta = .05$ then $RE \geq 1$.

From these examples, we can conclude that the advantage of SD over their FSD counterparts as measured by the RE depends upon α, β and h for fixed (θ_0, θ_1) .

V. TRUNCATED SEQUENTIAL TESTS

To prevent very long decision intervals, an SD is sometimes truncated at some maximum sample size (8), (9).

We shall consider an SD which has its boundaries modified as, $b G(n) < T_n < aG(n)$, where $G(n) = (1-n/N_T)$, and (a, b) are the thresholds of the untruncated SD. The function $G(n)$ is assumed bounded by $0 < G \leq 1$, and $n < N_T$, where N_T is the maximum allowed sample size. We must also assume, at the same time, that n is sufficiently large so that T_n converges to $N(0, 1)$ as explained in Section II.

From the F.I. we obtain the OC function as follows,

$$(14) \quad L(\delta) = (E_a(\exp(aGh)) - 1) / (E_a(\exp(aGh)) - E_b(\exp(bGh))),$$

where $E_a(\)$ and $E_b(\)$ represent average values, over n , which are functions of δ but conditioned on accepting H_1 or H_0 respectively.

The ASN follows as,

$$E_T(n/\delta) = (-2/hd) (aE_a(G)(1-L(\delta)) + bE_b(G)L(\delta)), \quad h \neq 0$$

$$(15)$$

$$E_T(n/\delta_c) = (-ab/d) (aE_a(G^2)E_b(G) - bE_b(G^2)E_a(G)) / (aE_a(G) - bE_b(G)),$$

$$\quad \quad \quad h = 0,$$

where $L(\delta_c) = aE_a(G) / (aE_a(G) - bE_b(G))$.

If under H_1 , $P(\delta) \sim 1$, then we obtain the result that,

$$E_T(n) \sim E_a(n).$$

A similar result is obtained under H_0 when $L(\delta_0) \sim 1$. The ASN, under H_1 , is given as follows, $E_T(n) = (2a/d) / (1 + 2a/dN_T)$. The ASN for the untruncated SD is expressed approximately as $E(n) \sim 2a/d$, so that the truncated SD can be given in terms of $E(n)$ under H_1 , as follows,

$$E_T(n) = E(n) / (1 + E(n)/N_T).$$

Similar results hold under H_0 .

Using a result from reference (8), we obtain the truncated type I error as,

$$\alpha_T \sim E_a(\exp(-aG)) = \exp(-a) E_a(\exp(an/N_T)).$$

By keeping only the first two terms of a Taylor series expansion of $\exp(-aG)$, we obtained the relationship $\alpha_T \sim a(1+aE(n))/(N_T + E(n))$.

The above results are consistent with the results obtained in reference (8) using our threshold function.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

We have investigated performance measures for sequential detectors in which the noise distribution is unknown and where the signal may deviate from its assumed alternative level during a decision period. The motivation for this current work is due, in part, to the results obtained in reference (2), where a robust array, for sequentially detecting weak stochastic signals in undefined noise, was designed based on partitioning the output of each sensor.

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